

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON THE TENSILE/COMPRESS BEHAVIOR OF STITCHED OPEN-HOLE STRUCTURES

Xi Liu, Ying Yan, Chuanxian Cheng, Dong Zeng, Bingshan Liu

School of Aeronautical Science and Engineering, BUAA, Beijing 100083, China

SUMMARY: Extensive experimental studies were carried out to investigate the effect of stitching on laminates' tensile and compressive properties. Different environmental conditions and stacking sequence were taken into consideration. Furthermore, specimens with center open-holes were tested. Test results indicate that stitching degraded specimens' tensile strength considerably, but with different Degradation Rate regarding to different stacking sequence, environment and specimen geometric configuration (with/without open-hole). However, stitching's effect on compressive properties varies. Further investigation shows that stitches significantly changed the failure mechanism of these tested specimens by suppressing the delamination and stabilizing the cracking speed, especially for the open-hole specimens.

KEYWORDS: stitching, environmental conditioning, experiment, failure mode, open-hole.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced laminates have been widely used, especially in Aerospace Industry. However, its relatively low interlaminar strength greatly limited its application on heavily loaded structures. Even under low energy impacts, delamination can initiate below the surface of the composite structures, which is hard to be detected through visual inspection. Under subsequent outer or inner loads, the delamination will spread rapidly, leading to catastrophic failure of these structures. Numerous techniques have been tried to enhance the interlaminar fracture strength, including toughened epoxy, thermoplastics, braiding, knitting, weaving and through thickness stitching. Because of its excellent shapeability and processability, stitching has gained considerable attention from the aerospace industry. Since the mid-1980s, considerable amount of research has been conducted to investigate stitching's influence on composite structures' mechanic properties, such as bending strength [1], laminates mode I and mode II fracture toughness [2,3,4], flexural properties [5,6], in-plane tensile and compression properties [4,7,8], compression after-impact (CAI) [1,4,9,10], However, relatively less attention was paid on the study of the mechanic properties of stitched structures with open-holes [5,11,12,13], which is quite common in aircraft structures, such as the bolt joints, gear door opening and access holes.

The objective of this paper is to investigate stitching effect on structures' static tensile and compressive properties in different test conditions. As described in the following section, three types of stacking sequence, a certain stitching density were considered.

EXPERIMENT SETUP AND PROCEDURE

Fabrication of Specimen

As shown in Fig.1, four groups of specimens were fabricated for this experimental study: Group A (25×250mm): Stitched/Unstitched specimens without central open-holes (Unnotched) were subject to tensile loads. Group B (38×50mm): Stitched/Unstitched specimens without central open-holes (Unnotched) were subject to compression loads. Group C (36×250mm): Stitched/Unstitched specimens with central open-holes (Notched) were subject to tensile loads. Group D (38×50mm): Stitched/Unstitched specimens with central open-holes (Notched) were subject to compression loads. All of them were fabricated by Resin Film Infusion (RFI). During the process, try unidirectional fabrics woven with T300 were laid up interleaved with layers of semi-solid resin film (made of QY9512), and then cured. As list in Table 1, in each group, there are three types of stacking sequence, named P-1, P-2 and P-3 respectively. For these stitched ones, the Kevlar 29 were used and the same stitching density was perform on these dry fabrics with the stitching row aligned parallel to the load axis (Stitching Column Spacing: 3mm, Stitching Row Spacing: 5mm). For the Open Hole Tension Test, as recommend by NASA-96-cr4751 [14], $\Phi 6$ mm holes were drilled to achieve a hole diameter ratio (W/d) of 6 (Fig. 1 (c)).

Table 1 Stacking Sequence

<i>Type</i>	<i>Stacking Sequence</i>	<i>Thickness: Stitched(mm)/ Unstitched (mm)</i>
P-1	[+45/0/-45/90] _{6s}	7.2/5.76
P-2	[0/+45/0/-45/90/-45/0/+45/0] _{2s}	5.4 /4.32
P-3	[90/+45/90/-45/0/-45/90/+45/90] _{2s}	5.4/4.32

*Figure 1. Dimensions of specimens:
(a) Group A; (b) Group B; (c) Group C; (d) Group D.*

Test Procedure

In this experiment, different techniques were applied to simulate three types of environmental conditions. They are: C-1: Room Temperature; C-2: Hot/wet condition, which was achieved by immersing specimens in distilled water at 71°C for periods of 200 hours, and then kept 150°C for 5 minutes; C-3: Hot condition, by Keeping 150°C for 5 minutes.

*Figure 2. Specimens on test fixtures:
(a) Tensile Tests in C-1; (b) Compression Tests in C-2, C-3.*

Before the tensile tests, specimens were firstly attached with end tabs on both ends to avoid any failure near the grips, then were fixed on the grips to make sure that load would act along the longitudinal axis of these specimens, as shown in Fig.2 (a). For the compression tests, a fixture (as present in Fig.2 (b)) was designed to align the outer compression load with the longitudinal direction of specimens, and avoided any side movement during test process.

A self-designed equipment was design to simulate hot environment (150 °C) for both tensile and compression tests. During the experiment procedure, the test facilities, as shown in Fig.2 (b), were assembled in a closed hot oven, in which a certain temperature was kept (150 °C for C-2 and C-3 condition in current experiment). A fan was used to provide homogenized temperature field around the test specimen.

During the test process, specimens were loaded at a constant displacement rate of 0.508 mm/min for all the tests until final failure, and failure tensile/compression loads were recorded. In order to obtain valid results, five identical specimens were tested per series.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Stitching on Tensile Properties

As bar chart given in Figure 3(a). After been stitched, the tensile strength of unnotched specimens dropped about 35.3%, 19.9% and 35.0% for P-1, P-2 and P-3 respectively. The same as that of the unnotched specimens, most of these notched specimens' tensile strength was mostly weakened after been stitched, by 13.7%, 14.8% and -1% (strengthened) for P-1, P-2 and P-3 respectively. Comparison of above tensile strength Degradation Rate indicates that the strength Degradation Rates of notched ones are much lower than that of unnotched

ones. This may attribute to the stitches effect to suppress the initiation of delamination along the open-hole edges, where high stress concentration and delamination always occur.

Figure 3. Tensile Strength of specimens in C-1

Figure 4. Stitched (Left)/Unstitched (Right) notched specimens after tensile tests

As the photograph of these tested specimens shows (Fig. 4), they broke invariably along transverse direction passing these open-holes. However, the failure mechanism of these plates was changed after stitching. The stitches stabilized the crack propagation by suppressing delaminations, and no-obvious delamination occurred. The failure paths always pass these stitch holes, where fiber breakage, resin-rich pockets and fiber misalignment are more likely to occur. On the other hand, for these unstitched ones, under tensile loads, delamination initiated from these edges near the top and bottom layers in vicinity of these open-holes. With increasing outer loads, delamination area spread rapidly accompanied by fiber breakage within these layers along the route normal to outer load axis. As the right five specimens shown in Fig. 4, more surface delamination can be observed, noticeably along the 45° direction.

Effect of Stitching on Compressive Properties

As Fig. 5 indicated, in C-1 condition, there is no any appreciable increase or decrease of the compression strength of both notched and unnotched specimens after been stitched by Kevlar29, with the increase/decrease rate mostly within 2%. However, the failure mode of the stitched/unstitched was significantly changed. During the test process, the delamination in unstitched specimens, mostly begin from the top layers near the open holes, when the outer compression loads increase to a certain point, the delamination area suddenly spread rapidly, accompanied by a sharp sound, then failed by sublaminar or global buckling. Large area of delamination can be observed on both the top and bottom faces as the right four specimens

present in Fig. 6. For the stitched specimens, the stitches successfully strengthened their interlaminar strength by arresting delaminations during the compression process. Compared with the unstitched ones, the cracks extended more gradual and steady, accompanied with matrix cracking and fiber buckling. The difference between notched and unnotched specimens is that the failures of the notched ones initiate from the open holes and spread along the transverse direction, however, the location of fail path of the unnotched ones' failure paths varies. Further investigation found that the notched specimens' compression strength dropped about 70~100MPa compared with unnotched ones with the same dimensions and environmental situation.

Figure 5. Compression Strength of specimens in C-1

Figure 6. Stitched (Left)/Unstitched (Right) notched specimens after compress tests

Effect of Environmental Condition

Three kinds of environment were taken into consideration as mentioned in the beginning of this paper. They are C-1: Room Temperature; C-2: Hot/Wet conditions (After been soaked and tried, the unstitched specimens contained 0.8~ 1.0 percent moisture and 1.0~1.2 percent for stitched ones); C-3: Hot Conditions.

As shown in Fig.7, although only test results for tensile tests in C-1, C-2 were obtained, the degradation trend for tensile/compression test under hot/wet condition could till be determined. For the unnotched specimens, their tensile strength dropped about 16% in C-2 than that in C-1. However, their compression strength degraded 35%~50% in C-2 and 20%~30% in C-3. The situation of the notched ones is nearly the same, just with larger scatter of Degradation Rate. Further investigation of these Degradation Rates indicates that for both notched and unnotched specimens, the tensile properties degraded much less than that of compressive properties in C-2. Matrix's sensitivity to hot/wet condition may accounts for this. In hot/wet conditions, matrix's mechanic properties deteriorate significantly, furthermore, the compressive strength depends on the matrix more [15].

Figure 7 (a) Tensile Strength of P-1 specimens; (b) Tensile Strength of notched specimens; (c) Compression Strength of unnotched specimens; (d) Compression Strength of notched specimens

It is also interesting to notice that in C-2, C-3, the compressive properties of stitched specimens dropped much less than those of unstitched. This phenomenon may also be attributed to the degradation of matrix properties due to hot/wet conditions. With a degraded matrix, the interlaminar strength would be seriously weakened. Cracks would initiate more easily between layers and expand rapidly. However, after being stitched, because stitches are relatively insensitive to hot/wet environments, they can still hold laminates together tightly, preventing the occurrence of delamination.

CONCLUSION

Experimental studies on the effect of stitching on the tensile/compressive properties of notched/unnotched specimens in different test conditions were carried out. From the test results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Stitching results in appreciable degradation of tensile properties of notched/unnotched specimens.
2. There were no significant changes in the compressive properties of the notched/unnotched specimens after being stitched.

3. Failure mode was obviously changed due to stitches' effect to suppress delamination. The failure process of these stitched specimens was more gradual and steady. And the delamination areas of them were much less than that of unstitched ones.
4. Comparison of these test results of specimens in C-1, C-2 and C-3 indicates that hot/wet condition would seriously deteriorate laminates tensile and compressive properties. Available results shows that the rank of specimens' strength in different test conditions is: In C-1, they have the highest tensile/compressive properties, then C-3, and their strength in C-2 is the lowest of the three.
5. Although stitching and open-hole' influence on specimens' tensile/compression strength varies with different stacking sequence, as these test results indicated, specimens with P-2 stacking sequence mostly exhibit highest tensile/compression strength in each test series.
6. Notched specimens' tensile/compression strength dropped less than that of unnotched ones after being stitched. Stitches' effect to prevent delamination initiation and spread near the open-hole edges may responsible for this. However, compared with that of unnotched specimens, open-holes invariably lowered specimens' tensile/compression strength. Thus, when designing composite components, unnecessary opening should be avoided.

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